

**MEANS AND METHODS OF FORMATION OF MORAL AND LEGAL
KNOWLEDGE IN THE CONTINUOUS EDUCATION SYSTEM**

Ergashev Humayun

Master of the National University of Uzbekistan

In the socio-philosophical literature, the concept of "innovative thinking" is widely used as a new category representing the intellectual abilities of a person at the current stage of society's development. Innovative thinking is a creative activity of society members aimed at creating material and spiritual wealth based on a new way of thinking, as a result of which the effectiveness of introducing innovations into the working process of existing systems becomes a priority. It is important to be able to deeply understand, understand and explain the possibilities of innovative thinking, to be able to apply its important and relevant aspects to relevant fields, to solve the problems of regulation and proper management of innovations in a timely manner. President Sh. Mirziyoev said: "Today, in order to renew and modernize our country, to develop it on an innovative basis, to implement the multi-faceted and complex tasks we have set before ourselves, we are modern and creative thinkers who can adapt to any situation. "We are entrusting important tasks in the management of the state and society to patriotic young personnel who are able to take responsibility, have high intellectual potential, and are enthusiastic." In scientific literature and official documents, a new way of thinking is called "innovative". "Innovative thinking" corresponds to the themes of modern understanding and technical-technological development. However, it should be noted that clear interpretations of this concept have not been formed, which, in turn, hinders mutual understanding, mutual clear and constructive conclusions, and implementation. The origin of the term "innovation" is derived from the Latin language. The Romans understood innovation, "renewal", "change" in a broad sense. Innovative activity is the integrated result of many processes with a complex structure. Therefore, it is important to consider its various aspects. In particular, one of the main issues in preparing young people for innovative activities is that in order to successfully implement this process, first of all, it is necessary to form young people's ability to think differently. This aspect of new thinking is distinguished by its specific features that "serve" innovative activity and ensure its effectiveness. We call this process of new thinking innovative thinking. The unique feature of innovative thinking is that it is inextricably linked not only with the high outlook of young people, but also with creative activity. It is not correct to associate such thinking only with mental models, considering that the mind is the only driving force of this process and the final result resulting from the material change of the environment. Because the innovative thinking in a person increases more and more through personal motivation, self-awareness, correct assessment of one's creative abilities, and effective use of them. "Today, we are moving on the path of innovative development aimed at radically renewing all spheres of state and community life. It's not for nothing, of course. Because in today's fast-paced world, who wins? The country that relies on a new idea, a new idea, and innovation will win." The active subject of the innovative society is young people, and at the current stage it is important to educate an innovative person in their image. American philosopher Everett Hagen brought the concept of "innovative person" into scientific circulation. Now, in today's conditions of social development, there is a special need to educate innovative individuals among the youth, who are the advanced stratum of society. Because only such young people occupy a special place in creating fundamental changes in the socio-economic life of society and in creating

innovations in the field of science. At the same time, in the formation of innovative thinking in such young people, the innovative approach and potential, the orientation of the activity to the creation of innovations, and the processes related to the formation of innovative thinking gain priority. Innovations become the criterion of human activity and form the basis of modern material and spiritual values. Therefore, creative people with modern innovative thinking can play an important role in our country. Creative individuals who meet the requirements of society and have leadership skills serve to form an innovative society by following high-potential individuals and organizing their activities. Innovation, being an objective process, is based on the intellectual work of subjects and is improved by them. Owners of innovative thinking are innovators, innovators, early adopters and other process stakeholders. As a result of the development of innovations, the creation of an innovative environment, consciousness, culture, goals and choices, the implementation of activities based on them, and the support of the activities of innovative groups become increasingly important. Therefore, "Culture," writes P. Kozlovsky, "today is recommended as the key to innovation and development of society, it facilitates the introduction of new technologies and "recognition" by society, helps to exchange international experience and mutual understanding. Culture should be in the range of all social indicators and growth criteria of society's development. Development of innovative thinking requires innovative behavior and implementation of innovative ideas. That is, people should be given the opportunity to implement their ideas and dreams in their lives. Because the need for every innovative idea must be covered by the consumer. Therefore, commercialization of ideas is one of the components of innovative thinking. Innovative thinking is the final result - income, it is a tool of any work, business development.

References:

1. Mirziyoev Sh. O'zbekiston yoshlariga bayram tabrigi // Xalqimizning roziligi bizning faoliyatimizga berilgan eng oliy bahodir. 2-jild. – T.: O'zbekiston, 2018. – B. 508.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh.Mirziyoevning Oliy Majlisga Murojaatnomasi. 2017 yil 22 dekabr. www.uza.uz.
3. Vasileva Ye. Zakonomernosti protsessa innovatsiy posledney chetverti XX veka. – Moskva: Ekonomika, 2007. –S. 5.
4. Gerasimova V., Mokichev S. Nano-economics in a National System of Innovation // Procedia Economics and Finance 5. 2013. Kazan (Russia) – P. 288-297.
5. Неъматов, О. Н. (2020). Шах маънавиятини юксалтиришда инновацион технологияларнинг методологик жиҳатлари. Science and Education, 1(1), 296-303.